

PACIFICUS

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“A COLLECTIVE VICTORY”

This is for you.

I just brought them home,
They are just in my hands,
But this is not all about me.

They speak about you—yes, you—
Who keep me inspired and motivated to work.

They are about learners
Who never fail to ignite passion and creativity.

They are about my colleagues and friends
For making the job bearable and fun.

They are about my superiors, past and present
Who showered me with trust and confidence.

They are about the community
For the love you reach out.

They are about my family
Who loves me whole, making things possible.

PACIFICUS EDITORIAL TEAM

Managing Editor: Roger B. Rueda, PhD

Managing Director: Kevin F. Suaganog, MED

Proprietor/Head Designer: Bryan G. Gamarcha

New Poblacion, Buenavista, Guimaras

They are about God
Who is behind this growth.

These awards belong to everyone
Because I cannot fly alone, without you.

For you made me spread my wings,
Let me share this victory with you
By saying my sincerest "Thank You."

This is about you.

(You may also read the last line and up.)

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